

Chairman,
Parliamentary Committee on Constitutional and Legal matters,
Parliament House,,
Accra.

Dear sir

**MEMO AGAINST THE PASSING OF THE BILL
PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES
BILL 2021**

Please find attached my Memo on the above subject.

I am a Ghanaian citizen in my mid seventies and wish to add my voice to the debate on this bill.

I have also included to this attachment a pen drive carrying a soft copy version of the memo.

Yours faithfully,

M [redacted] K [redacted] M [redacted]

House # C13 / A / D54

Sakumono Estates

GPS 376 – 0208

MEMO AGAINST THE PASSING OF THE BILL - PROMOTION OF PROPER HUMAN SEXUAL RIGHTS AND GHANAIAN FAMILY VALUES BILL 2021

Abstract

This memo is of the opinion that the central issue of criminalization of homosexuality in the bill was not well addressed. The bill failed to do a detailed work on what homosexuality is. It failed to establish if it is a choice or a genetic deviation. It did not indicate the features of a homosexual for ease of identification. The bill espoused on a subject it did not have full knowledge about; and because of this position, the clauses in the bill can be described as recklessly discriminatory

If passed into law as it is now, it would be a recipe for intolerance, mayhem and homophobia as anyone could be labeled a homosexual. It should be withdrawn. Existing laws which have dealt with issues of unnatural carnal knowledge should be reviewed to deal with any section of the population, be it homosexual, heterosexual, bisexual, etc.

Introduction

Honourable members of Parliament, I greet you in the name of God. I thank you for the approach you have adopted to ensure that this bill is widely discussed as far as possible. I appreciate the clause by clause debate approach for getting the bill approved as suggested by the Minority leader. Other members of this honourable house have also categorically stated that they would not succumb to threats that they would not be voted for if they did not support the bill. I pray the almighty God continues to give you the wisdom to see you through this national assignment.

May God grant us the sobriety of mind, as a country to bring this discussion to an acceptable conclusion.

About myself:

I am Michael Kofi Mensah a Christian and a citizen. I am in my mid seventies; a pensioner and dabbles as a consultant in Planning and Management.

I must state emphatically without any equivocation that I do not and will never support homosexual acts; but as a christian I will love homosexuals as creatures of God; and I will not discriminate against them.

Opening remarks

In the form that it is presented, this bill will ignite intolerance which will most likely lead to homophobia and unnecessary damage to innocent lives and property.

It will put the country into a situation of alertness where miscreants could take the law into their hands to determine who is a homosexual. Two females or two males cannot enjoy their lives without looking over

their shoulders to see who may want to descend on them, on the presumption that they are lesbians or gays.

Young men with tattoos and plaited or braided hair styles cannot go about without being labeled as homosexuals. Ladies cannot be seen smoking and drinking as a group without being associated with homosexual traits.

Landlords could be scared and would not want to rent their homes to bachelors and spinsters on the grounds that they could be homosexuals.

Do not pass this bill as presented. It is TALABANIC with total disregard for **basic human rights** and designed to lower our level of tolerance for each other.

What is the Bill about?

The bill is a product of consensus among some aggrieved persons following news reports in January 2021, that LGBTQ+ advocacy resource centre was being opened in Accra. The bill in essence seeks to stem the growth of LGBTQ+ tendencies through the punishment of persons expressing themselves as homosexuals, persons engaged in the act; any one purporting to be an advocate or lending support, or media purporting to be propagating homosexual rights in Ghana. The bill prescribed various levels of penalties for persons falling foul to the law.

What is wrong with this Bill?

Lacks in-depth definition of Homosexuality.

Poor technical analysis of homosexuality and the prevalence of HIV

Has no basis to show the growth of the homosexual population and by extension homosexual acts

Failed to draw a line between sin / family life and crime

Failed to establish features to enable separate homosexuals from straights

Failed to align bill with established National and International Human Rights Standards.

Failed to establish relationships between the UN / SDGs and issue of homosexuality as espoused in the bill.

What my memo seeks to do.

This memo seeks to address the wrongs in the bill. It would highlight weaknesses in the justification upon which clauses and bill were founded. In this memo, I would limit myself to homosexuality with the belief other members of the group share common features.

I would commence with establishing a wider understanding of homosexuality before correcting issues raised in the bill, which border on inaccuracies or nebulous.

Who is a homosexual / homosexuality

The bill as presented failed to define homosexuals and homosexuality. What it did was to continuously mention the group LGBTQQ and on page 23 only tell readers what the individual abbreviations stand for. It failed woefully, whether by design or not to define what homosexual or homosexuality act is about.

According to the following sources:

Longman Dictionary of Contemporary English:

A homosexual is someone, especially a man, who is sexually attracted to people of the same sex.

Wikipedia copiously defines it:

As a romantic attraction, sexual attraction, or sexual behavior between members of the same sex or gender.[1][2][3] As a sexual orientation, homosexuality is "an enduring pattern of emotional, romantic, and/or sexual attractions" to people of the same sex. It "also refers to a person's sense of identity based on those attractions, related behaviors, and membership in a community of others who share those attractions." [4][5]

Along with bisexuality and heterosexuality, homosexuality is one of the three main categories of sexual orientation within the heterosexual–homosexual continuum.[4] **Scientists do not yet know the exact cause of sexual orientation, but they theorize that it is caused by a complex interplay of genetic, hormonal, and environmental influences**[6][7][8] **and do not view it as a choice.**[6][7][9] Although no single theory on the cause of sexual orientation has yet gained widespread support, scientists favor biologically-based theories.[6] There is considerably **more evidence supporting nonsocial, biological causes of sexual orientation than social ones, especially for males.**[10][11][12] There is no substantive evidence which suggests parenting or early childhood experiences play a role with regard to sexual orientation.[13] **While some people believe that homosexual activity is unnatural,**[14] **scientific research shows that homosexuality is a normal and natural variation in human sexuality and is not in and of itself a source of negative psychological effects.**[4][15] There is insufficient evidence to support the use of psychological interventions to change sexual orientation (en.m.wikipedia.org)

L.J. Gooren, W. Byne, in *Hormones, Brain and Behavior* (Third Edition), 2017- explains

The overwhelming majority of biomedical studies into homosexuality have searched for signs and symptoms of biological femaleness in homosexual men and biological maleness in homosexual women. Some studies (digit ratios, fraternal birth order, abnormal hormonal milieu in prenatal life, and brain structure) have indeed found statistically significant associations but the results fail to provide a comprehensive explanation as to why some people are attracted to members of the same sex, while the majority are not. Broader research into the general principles of sexual orientation beyond the search for evidence of cross-sex differentiation of the brain would enhance not only our understanding of homosexuality but also of heterosexuality.

Richard E. Jones PhD, Kristin H. Lopez PhD, in *Human Reproductive Biology* (Fourth Edition), 2014 – Write on treatment

Should homosexuality be treated? A prevailing viewpoint is that a homosexual should seek professional help only if being gay makes them unhappy. Traditionally, psychologists or psychiatrists have found that it is difficult to “treat” a homosexual. **Masters and Johnson**, however, report success not only in treating **sexual dysfunction in homosexuals, but also in eliminating homosexual tendencies in about two-thirds of those who wished to change their sex-object choice.** Some critics of their findings feel that the patients studied were really mostly

bisexuals, as a majority of the “homosexuals” treated by Masters and Johnson were rated as having scores of 3 or 4 on the Kinsey scale.

Is homosexual orientation reversible?

As adduced from the definitions above, there is yet no evidence that it is reversible. Individuals are born with the orientation. It is a natural way of life for those born that way.

Whilst accepting that it a genetic issue for which there is no answer, there is no gainsaying that other persons may also have acquired this trait through association with natural homosexuals. The pertinent issue to ask is, “has the bill differentiated between the two?”.

For the sake of emphasis, there is a minority of individuals whose make-up is naturally homosexual; and these have every human right like any of us. And this has not been catered for under the bill.

Whilst one may not subscribe to homosexuality from varying point of views, it is an incontrovertible fact that some persons are naturally born that way. From this angle therefore, a bill of this nature must strive to attack only those that are deviants or miscreants; definitely not the natural homosexual as the bill as presented seeks to do. The bill failed to do that and therefore qualifies as a bill that discriminates against a minority and therefore tramples on rights.

The bill was cast in a way that did not take **cognizance of the existence of genetically born homosexuals**.

Homosexuals and rights

If time is taken to understand what homosexual is, the question of whether they have rights or not would have arisen. It would have carried a positive response. If it is agreed that homosexuals are human beings just as the heterosexuals but do not share the sexual persuasions, then let it be. They cannot be denied of their basic rights as enshrined in both the constitution of Ghana and the International Covenant on Civil and political Rights of which Ghana is a signatory. Ghana’s Constitution in Article 21 establishes basic rights such as freedom of speech, thought, conscience, belief and association amongst others.

And similarly, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) which Ghana signed in 1975,states it in Article 18 as follows:

1. Everyone shall have the right to freedom of thought, conscience and religion. This right shall include freedom to have or to adopt a religion or belief of his choice, and freedom, either individually or in community with others and in public or private, to manifest his religion or belief in worship, observance, practice and teaching.
2. No one shall be subject to coercion which would impair his freedom to have or to adopt a religion or belief of his choice.
3. Freedom to manifest one's religion or beliefs may be subject only to such limitations as are **prescribed by law and are necessary to protect public safety, order, health, or morals or the fundamental rights and freedoms** of others.

Homosexual and infringement on the rights of others

As evident in the third paragraph of Article 18 of the ICCPR, freedom can be curtailed to protect public safety, order, health, or morals or the fundamental rights and freedoms of others. **And this is absolutely fair. But** the bill under review failed to establish convincingly the rights of others being trampled upon.

The bill apart from stating issues of public health and morals did not present evidence to support this claim. Homosexuals as defined are a minority and do not pose such a danger to health and morality as being propounded in the bill. The homosexual act may be abominable but does not warrant such a bill to stem its growth, if at all.

In Ghana, do persons of different persuasions, of religion and culture live in harmony? Why will homosexuals not also be accommodated?

The key issue to consider is the homosexual as a person created by God like all others vis -a - vis his homosexual act which may be considered by us as unacceptable.

Do we not have homes in which the father and head of the household is a traditional believer (idol worshipper) and children, because of secular education, are practicing Christians? The children do not go the way of the father; and the father does not interfere with the religious beliefs of his children.

Take a look at the number of religious faiths around. No one should believe that they are not subtly fighting to win converts into their own religious persuasion; but are they fighting a war of conversion. What each religious sect does is to be resilient and thwart the efforts of any intruding religious faith.

Homosexuality is abominable and could be detestable depending on one's persuasion.; but instead of fighting it through criminalization and denying them their rights; let those who abhor it, make themselves resilient and allow it not to intrude into their families.

By all means lets fashion laws which penalize offenders not because of what they are but rather for the offence / acts they have committed. If a gay is picked up for indecent exposure or amorous relationship; same also should apply to a heterosexual.

A mix-up between morality and crime

The bill slants more in line with religious moral values. Nowhere was the bill able to substantiate the criminal intent embodied in homosexuality or find fault with being a homosexual person. NOWHERE.

Many have argued that it is against God's command. No one in his right mind should dispute this because it is a sin. But since when has ordinary mortal, of imperfection, become a judge of sins?

A sin is a sin, and its between you and your God; whilst a crime is between you and your God and man. For those bending towards the issue of criminalizing moral / sin issue, I ask, what is the crime for not worshipping God? Yet that is the first of the ten commandments God gave to Moses. Who punishes you for not worshipping the one and only God the people believe in? So in essence, not all sins are crimes.

In my opinion, for a crime to have been committed there must be a victim. If a thief steals, he / she has committed a crime of stealing, (unlawfully depriving another person of his / her bona fide possession) which is punishable by law. Similarly, killing is a sin and a crime punishable by law. Honour your father and mother is a commandment which when violated is a sin but not a punishable crime.

Take Female Genital mutilation widely practised in many communities in Ghana in the name of culture; it took international institutions many years to fight against it, until it was and criminalized. Is it a sin or a crime? It may not be a sin to the one carrying out the mutilation because of tradition but in the eyes of the law, there is a victim, and so it is a crime.

Kleptomania is an impulse control disorder that results in an irresistible urge to steal. The cause of kleptomania remains unknown; but risk factors include a family history of kleptomania or other impulse control disorders. It occurs more in women. **Treatment can help but can't be cured. Can last for life. (Source: Mayo Clinic goggled).**

Being a carrier of kleptomania does not free the kleptomaniac who engages in the crime of stealing from being punished. The kleptomaniac in spite of the disorder has deprived someone of his/her possession. This is the case of stealing and aptly a sin and crime; a crime because there is a victim or sufferer of the act of stealing..

If homosexuality (a disorder of sex orientation) is juxtaposed against kleptomania (also a disorder) it is the moral sinful aspect of homosexuality that is **discerned whilst the criminal dimension is not apparent compared to one in which a kleptomaniac steals.**

At what point has the homosexual committed a crime as the bill seeks to portray? When did expressing one's self- identity become a crime? And who is the victim? The originators of the bill can do better.

Issues against certain portions of the justification from pages 1-9

Homosexuals and HIV

The bill made claims in page 5 with reference to a 2017 report of the Science Research Council that 18.1% of people living with Aids are gays (MSM).

Available information on HIV (Ghana Aids Commission Documentation) for the period 2015 – 2019 showed that the prevalence rate had dropped by 0.11% and was projected to reduce by 0.09% in 2020; with a national prevalence rate for 2020 pegged at 1.70%.

The following information was also noted.

1. Prevalence is high among pregnant women
2. Prevalence rate is high among Female sex workers
3. Males form 34% of 346,120 PLWHIV
4. Females make up 66% of 346,120 PLWHIV

Interestingly, the following Regions have prevalence rates higher than the national average of 1.70% of adults PLWHIV:

1. Bono – 2.66%
2. Greater Accra – 2.47%
3. Eastern – 2.07%
4. Ashanti – 1.94%

The above has been deliberately discussed here, not because this memo seeks to disclaim the potential dangers of HIV but rather, it seeks to bring to the fore that other key populations are at even greater risk than the MSM which has been viciously focused on in the bill.

It may be interesting to know why Bono's prevalence rate is higher than that of Greater Accra or Kumasi where the activities of homosexuality are presumably higher.

Is the population of homosexuals growing?

Generally, a good justification in project design and proposal is trend analysis; and cannot be different for the writing of a bill of this nature. But this is deficient in the proposed bill. The bill created “a mountain out of a mole hill” scenario just to create a basis for the Clauses to follow in the bill. This is made apparent in pages 4 and 5.

The bill indicated that 18.1% MSM population contributed to the incidence of HIV but failed to draw attention to the contributors making the the remaining 82%. But what is factual is that the incidence of adult males to HIV in 2019 / 2020 was 34% (122,321) of adult population of PLWHIV. In other words, the 18.1% referred to is an integral part of the total adult male population of PLWHIV.

What the bill could have done was to show the trend of the growth of MSM which would require drastic action as being promoted by the bill. In some other jurisdictions such analysis are vital in making policy decisions.

Below is an illustration.

In October 2012, Gallup started conducting annual surveys to study the demographics of LGBT people, determining that 3.4% ($\pm 1\%$) of adults identified as LGBT in the United States.^[137] It was the nation's largest poll on the issue at the time.^{[138][139]} In 2017, the percentage was estimated to have risen to 4.5% of adults, with the increase largely driven by Millennials. The poll attributes the rise to greater willingness of younger people to reveal their sexual identity.^[140]

Gallup polling of U.S. adults identifying as LGBT per year						
Date of birth	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017
1913–1945	1.8%	1.8%	1.9%	1.5%	1.5%	1.4%
1946–1964	2.7%	2.7%	2.7%	2.6%	2.4%	2.4%
1965–1979	3.2%	3.3%	3.4%	3.3%	3.2%	3.5%
1980–1999	5.8%	6.0%	6.3%	6.7%	7.3%	8.2%

What this bill is drumming home now is that HIV through homosexuality demands immediate action as a justification for the bill but this is not backed by adequate data.

Presently HIV ranks sixth in the list of Ghana’s top ten causes of death diseases.

Quote of the supreme court

The bill on page 5 quoted a 2014 judgement verdict of the the Supreme Court in support of its justification.

The judgement reads as follows:

“it is the female sex organs called the vulva and vagina that are **normally** penetrated into during sexual act which can qualify to be carnal knowledge under sections 98 and 99 of Act 29”

For the advocates of the bill to fall on this judgement as a strong justification conveys the difficulties in drawing a bill of this nature.

From my lay man point of view, the judges in their pronouncement were not categorical. The key word used was “NORMALLY”. And this connotes that, there could be other ways which the judgement was silent on. I do not think this is supportive enough for the bill.

SDGs and the Bill

The bill fell copiously on the UN adopted Agenda 2030 and claimed the SDGs especially Goals 3, 5 and 10 supported the thrust of the bill. The bill flogged the SDGs in a futile exercise not sufficient to justify the framing of the bill.

The bill claims to be in line with the spirit of SDG 10.3.1; and in the opinion of the framers, the bill seeks to prohibit the abuse or harassment of suspected homosexuals. But this is not evident in a bill which makes it an offence for anyone expressing him / herself as a homosexual.

For brevity, it is apt to state that no UN adopted programme or policy no matter how framed frowns on the rights on any group of persons. It is therefore spurious to draw support from the the SDGs, no matter the latitude given to member countries to align the spirit of the 2030 agenda to local conditions.

Issues against the clauses

The clauses of the bill evolved from the justification profusely presented in pages one to nine. In my opinion the justification did not do justice to the key issues of homosexuality. And in this wise many of the clauses are not meritorious because they are directed at penalizing a group of persons who the bill did not try to know much about and who also do not share an identity with a majority group.

A number of the clauses is an imposition of the standards of the majority on the minority. For instance clause one and two limit the right of self expression of identity. What offence is committed if someone expresses him / herself as a homosexual? Who is hurt?

Clauses 8 and 7 applies to all sexual persuasions and should not be limited to homosexuals

Clause 10 talks of gross indecency. Gross indeceny is not permissible even in the so call heterosexual sub- kingdom.

Clause 12 totally tramples on the right of a minority to use technology to project their cause. This amounts to total suppression of a minority group.

Clause 13 on children can adequately be catered for under laws pertaining to the rights of children.

Clause 15 and 16 on association, is heinous. Can persons who share common identity not associate? The constitution guarantees freedom of any association, in so far as the activities of the association has not been proven beyond reasonal doubts to be inimical to society.

For brevity, it is the considered opinion that the bill should be taken back and re-examined clause by clause based on a better understanding of what homosexuality. This has been poorly undertaken in this bill for reasons best known to the framers..

Miscellaneous

Society and acculturation

Acculturation is defined as a process of learning and incorporating the values, beliefs, language, customs and mannerisms of a new country or group. And society has always thrived under acculturation.

Judges, Lawyers, parliament, our judicial, legal and parliamentary systems today do things the way they are done because of acculturation. How does the speaker attire himself? Does he choose to attire himself in whatever manner he wants?

I have looked round and can I identify a list of things we do which have been influenced by other cultures. Do you go about putting sponge (koosha in Ga) in your mouth as was done some fifty years ago? Do we use the traditional health care giver as was done many years ago? Things have changed and the world is moving forward.

One thing about cultures is that only a good culture can thrive. No “bad “culture” can be forced on a people for long before it reverts to another which is more supportive of the cause of the people.

Let us build a resilient society; a society in which our children can outrightly reject a behavior, practice or custom out of volition rather than criminalization. If we make our children resilient, they will abhor homosexuality even in an environment in which it is liberal.

Dealing with a recalcitrant homosexual son / daughter.

This paragraph of my memo seeks to draw attention of the framers to pertinent family issues in relation to the bill.

It starts with this, “What steps would any of us take should we find ourselves dealing with a transgender son?” He / she has served you without any blemish only for you to get a note that daddy I am now a girl and I am so very happy that I have discovered myself.

Do you go to the police to report, “my son has transgendered, come and arrest him?” That is the spirit of this bill as it is now. A self-professed homosexual is a criminal and the person who keeps him / her knowing that him / her is a self – professed homosexual also commits a crime under this bill.

Many of us today have brothers and sisters, children and family members who are rogues. We live with them and see them go to perform their trade (of havoc) and yet we do not give them up. Are their acts not worse than homosexuals?

Homosexuality and heterosexuality compared

The modus operandi of the homosexual and heterosexual are the same with the only difference being that one leads to making babies and the other does not.

Both make advances to catch their suitors. They both make themselves appealing and lure their suitors with cash and presents.

About offences: both can commit rape / defilement which in the case of the homosexual can be labeled as sodomy.

So, without being selective let us have laws that are not discriminatory but instead have laws that are encompassing to take care of gross sexual indecencies in society.

Conclusion

Homosexuality is an abhorring act to a majority in society of heterosexual majority. Research has shown that it is historical and many find it abominable.

In this memo, I am submitting that homosexuality as the focus of the bill of “promotion of proper sexual and family values” has not been well expounded. The bill glossed over issues, such as whether homosexuality is a choice and treatable or one that is biologically driven and for which treatment and period of incarceration cannot be a solution

If a fuller and better treatment of homosexuality had been pursued, the outcome of the issues presented in the various clauses of the bill would not be what they are.

This memo calls for the withdrawal of this bill, which was drafted as a response to events of January 2021 as an assignment hurriedly undertaken with vendetta.

The bill failed to put an operational definition on how to recognize a homosexual. Is he a man who wears ladies dress with ear- rings and tattoos over the body? Nowhere was this done; and in so doing, the bill if passed will embolden people to witch- hunt on homosexual in a frenzy and homophobic manner.

Whilst I do not subscribe to homosexual activities, it is my view that the bill failed to nail on the head the crime for being a homosexual. It totally labeled homosexuals as evil and did not see anything wrong with evils perpetrated by heterosexuals.

To sum up, the fight against the advancement of homosexuality must be a national crusade of teaching and counseling children on the right things to do rather than being an issue for criminalization. If children are taught the essence of procreation, family values and self-identity; they would be resilient and hold onto those values, and no amount of sugar-coated talks would draw them into homosexuality or obscene heterosexuality.

For a way forward, presently persons are convicted for sodomy, defilement etc. based on existing laws; and these existing laws should be reviewed for wider application

Sex education and the values of family life should be intensified at homes, churches and mosques.

Multiple sex partners should be discouraged

Patronage of sex workers should be discouraged

Citizens be taught the essence of abstinence before marriage, faithfulness in marriage and the use of condoms, if need be.

The Media to be circumspect with what they show on TV and broadcast

And above all let's live a prayerful and righteous life in which we are each other's keeper

